

Surgical Visual Understanding: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Surgical Visual Understanding

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

SurgVU

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Growing at an exponential rate with well over a million cases performed each year, robotic assisted surgery (RAS) promises to transform surgical intervention. Both the nature of the data these cases produce, and the sheer amount of it, present altogether new possibilities for study. Pursuits such as the quantification of surgical performance, efficiency and tool choreography, OR resource planning, AI-guided surgical planning, and surgical data science in general can all exploit this new source of clinical data. Not surprisingly, machine learning techniques that can extract meaning from these vast amounts of data seem poised to play an integral role. With this goal in mind we invite the surgical data science community to take part in two challenges, utilizing the largest publicly available dataset released to date (840+ hours of data). The first sub challenge requires participants to build a model that localizes tools and their corresponding key-points in videos, using only tool presence data. The second sub challenge invites participants to segment videos into different surgical steps being performed. Winning solutions will help advance surgical assistive technologies significantly.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

computer vision, machine learning, surgical data science, surgical tool detection, surgical activity recognition

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

N/A

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

N/A

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

EndoVis challenge

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

30+ teams

Two of our previous challenges (SurgToolLoc 2022/23) had 18 and 23 participating teams (please check out <https://surgtoolloc23.grand-challenge.org/teams/> and <https://surgtoolloc.grand-challenge.org/teams/>). We expect the number of participating teams to grow based on the added tasks, our growing reputation, and the additional publicity of the Lighthouse status.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We will be coordinating a joint publication with the teams after the challenge is complete

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The challenge will be conducted online on grand-challenge.org. The only space/hardware requirements would be of standard conference venue room and computer/projector/audio for challenge presentations.

TASK 1: Surgical tool detection

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The ability to automatically detect and track surgical instruments in endoscopic video will enable many transformational interventions. Assessing surgical performance and efficiency, identifying skilled tool use and choreography, and planning operational and logistical aspects of OR resources are just some of the applications that would benefit. The annotations needed to train machine learning models to robustly identify and localize surgical tools, however, are difficult to obtain. Annotating bounding boxes frame-by-frame in video is tedious and time consuming, yet a wide variety of surgical tools and surgeries must be captured for robust training. Moreover, ongoing annotator training is needed to stay up to date with surgical instrument innovation. In robot-assisted surgery, potentially informative data like timestamps of instrument installation and removal, can be programmatically harvested. The ability to use only tool presence labels to localize tools would significantly reduce the annotation workload needed to train robust tool detection, localization, and tracking models. In this challenge, we invite the surgical data science community to leverage tool presence data as weak labels to train machine learning models to localize and classify tools with bounding boxes in video frames.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

computer vision, machine learning, object detection, object tracking, surgical tool detection

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Aneeq Zia (Intuitive), Max Berniker (Intuitive), Conor Perreault (Intuitive), Rogerio Nespolo (Intuitive), Anthony Jarc (Intuitive)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Aneeq Zia (aneeq.zia2@intusurg.com)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event (MICCAI) with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

N/A

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Only automatic methods will be allowed

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Any publicly available dataset will be allowed for pre-training. Any private dataset used will need to be released publicly at the time of submission.

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May participate and be visible on leaderboard, but will not be eligible for awards

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

3 monetary prizes for 1st, 2nd , and 3rd place – exact amount per task to be decided

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Complete leaderboard will be visible publicly on the challenge website. The top 3 teams for each tasks will also be announced within the prizes sub-page of the challenge website

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The organizers will publish a challenge paper within 6 months of the challenge day. All participating teams with valid submission will be eligible for being part of this combined paper. Following this publication, the participating teams will be allowed to publish their own results from the challenge citing the challenge paper.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The teams will need to submit an algorithm container (type 2) on grand-challenge. Detailed instructions will be provided to the teams on how to create such containers and submit them along with example submission containers.

Check out a submission instructions page from one of our previous challenge at <https://surgtolloc23.grand-challenge.org/submission-instructions/>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

There will be preliminary testing phases for each task where the teams will be allowed multiple (up to 10) algorithm submissions for testing. The dataset within these preliminary testing phases will only be 10-15% of the actual testing data set. The final rankings of the teams will only be based on their algorithm performances on the final testing phase submission.

Please check out an example preliminary and final testing phase leaderboards from one of our previous challenges below:

Prelim testing - <https://surgtolloc23.grand-challenge.org/evaluation/challenge/leaderboard/>

Final testing - <https://surgtolloc23.grand-challenge.org/evaluation/final-testing-phase/leaderboard/>

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)

- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

An estimated timetable is given below

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Start of preliminary testing phase: 1st June, 2025

Start of final test phase: 5th August, 2025

New registrations deadline: 26th August, 2025

End of preliminary testing phase: 2nd September, 2025

End of final test phase: 10th September, 2025

Methodology reports (with all submission requirements) due: 20th September, 2025

Winners announced: On challenge day at MICCAI 2025

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Code availability

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The code to generate the evaluation metrics within the evaluation container (in grand-challenge) will be made public through a github repo.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participating teams will be required to make their algorithm container generating code public through a github repo.

An example of such a repo by a team in our previous challenge can be checked at https://github.com/vu-maple-lab/surgtool_challenge

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizing team (all within Intuitive) will have access to test cases and labels, hence there will be no conflict of interest with any other institution. All awards will also be sponsored by Intuitive, while any team from within Intuitive wanting to participate will not be eligible for any award.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Surgical tasks performed on porcine model by trainees during robotic surgical training. Tasks include suturing of different styles (1-hand, 2-hand, running), and dissection performed on various anatomy (uterine horn, rectal vein/artery, etc.). Tools include (but are not limited to) graspers, needle drivers, scissors, staplers, clip appliers, and energy instruments

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Surgical tasks performed on porcine model by trainees of various skill levels during robotic surgical training

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Single channel of endoscopic video

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The training videos will come with ground truth tool presence labels along with surgical step labels while the testing data will have ground truth tool bounding box labels along with surgical step labels.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

n/a

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data will be acquired from basic tasks being performed on a porcine model using a da Vinci Xi or Si system

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Prediction of surgical tool bounding boxes.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

For bounding box detection, the assessment will be done using mean average precision over multiple intersection-over-union (IOU) values - this metric is standard for COCO dataset.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The Intuitive Data Recorder (IDR) will be used to capture video at 720p and 30fps from one channel of the endoscope on da Vinci Xi or Si system

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The videos will be captured at 720p and 30fps from one channel of the endoscope on da Vinci Xi or Si system

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data will be collected at 2 Intuitive Surgical training labs

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Experience of study participants will mostly be beginners (early in their learning curve) with a few experts (practicing surgeons) if possible.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case in this challenge will comprise of a video of a surgical training being performed on a porcine model. These videos will be long and variable in length where multiple surgical training steps will be present in each video along with different surgical tools.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

We will have 200+ cases for training and 50+ for testing. We will ensure variability in the dataset through the variety of tasks completed on the porcine model on different anatomy. Each case has an average length of around 4 hrs.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The numbers indicated were kept keeping in mind data collection technicalities and to provide enough data to the participants for developing meaningful models

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

We will try to ensure that the dataset has a balanced range of different tools and surgical steps within the training and testing set. We expect our dataset to have around 10+ unique tool labels with unequal distribution across classes (as some tools occur much more often than other e.g. needle driver) while the surgical step distribution will be much more balanced across training and testing sets.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

N/A

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

We will use a crowd to annotate tool bounding boxes for our testing set. The annotations will not be redundant as bounding box annotations are not that subjective. The surgical step annotations will be done by a team of domain knowledge experts for training and testing sets.

At least 5 annotators for bounding boxes and 2-3 annotators for step annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For test set annotation, the crowd-sourced annotators were already trained and experienced in spatial annotation for surgical tools. Each frame will be annotated then reviewed by the annotation team to ensure quality. Bounding box labels will be placed around the surgical tools along with an object ID for object tracking. Additional tool classification label, such as left or right side will also be annotated. For surgical steps, the annotators will be provided by clear step starting and ending times for annotations.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Annotators will have significant experience in labelling bounding boxes for surgical tools and surgical steps.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

n/a

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Raw video frames will not be altered

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Image annotation will only be needed for the test set. Main sources of error would include the bounding box not being "tight" around the tool. It's hard to estimate the error quantitatively but we don't expect it to be more than 5%. For surgical steps, there can be some sources of error as this type of annotation is temporal in nature. However, as the robotic surgical training steps are very well defined (as opposed to steps in clinical procedures), we do not expect there to be any significant error in annotations (<5%)

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

The tool presence labels will be generated using the events stream from the da Vinci system. There is a possibility of a dropped event that can cause error in the training tool presence labels. However, we do not expect this to happen frequently. The step labels would not have any other relevant source of error.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Mean average precision (mAP) for different intersection over union (IoU) values 0.50:0.05:0.95 will be used to assess performance of tool bounding box prediction algorithms.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

This is the standard metric used for bounding box prediction algorithms (and is also the COCO primary challenge metric). By varying the thresholds, this metric provides a more thorough evaluation of tool localization/keypoint detection accuracy. The surgical step category is a standard classification problem where average f1-score can accurately measure the performance of the models. This metric has proven to be a good measure of model performances in our previous challenges as well.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The performance rank will be based on the rank of the evaluation metric (e.g mAP IoU 0.5:0.05:0.95 for bounding box detection) - the higher the value of this metric, the higher the ranking of that team will be.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results will be penalized and no score will be given for those cases

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Using the standard metrics being used within the object detection research seems like the right way to rank teams. The spatial detection metric tests the algorithms for detection of objects of different sizes (for tool detection category) which will be useful in differentiating high and low performing teams. Similarly, mean f1-score will reward and penalize the predictions for correct/incorrect predictions accordingly.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,

- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Standard statistical methods to test for significance in results like t-test, ANOVA etc., will be used. Bootstrapping will also be used for uncertainty analysis.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The stated statistical methods are fairly standard and used extensively in literature to test for statistical significance and uncertainty of prediction models.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Additional analysis will be performed on the results to check for ranking variability. On top of the mAP across multiple IoU values for the first category, we will test ranking of the teams when using individual IoU values (e.g. 0.5, 0.6, etc) instead of averaging over all. In addition to this, we will evaluate per class metrics as well.

TASK 2: Surgical step recognition

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Machine learning models that can detect surgical activities being performed from endoscopic video will enable transformational interventions. For example, it can allow for improved assessments of surgical performance, efficiency, and tool choreography, as well as new analyses of OR resource planning. In this challenge we invite the surgical data science community to build models that can segment videos into different surgical steps being performed within robotic-assisted training. High performing models in this challenge will help in automatically recognizing steps in surgical procedures that can enable many downstream applications e.g generating step based objective performance reports

Keywords

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ORGANIZATION

Organizers

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MICCAI 2025

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Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizing team (all within Intuitive) will have access to test cases and labels, hence there will be no conflict of interest with any other institution. All awards will also be sponsored by Intuitive, while any team from within Intuitive wanting to participate will not be eligible for any award.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Surgical tasks performed on porcine model by trainees during robotic surgical training. Tasks include suturing of different styles (1-hand, 2-hand, running), and dissection performed on various anatomy (uterine horn, rectal vein/artery, etc.). Tools include (but are not limited to) graspers, needle drivers, scissors, staplers, clip applicators, and energy instruments

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Surgical tasks performed on porcine model by trainees of various skill levels during robotic surgical training

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Single channel of endoscopic video

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The training videos will come with ground truth tool presence labels along with surgical step labels while the testing data will have ground truth tool bounding box labels along with surgical step labels.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

n/a

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data will be acquired from basic tasks being performed on a porcine model using a da Vinci Xi or Si system

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Prediction of surgical step being performed.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

For surgical step classification task, average f1-score across all steps will be used for evaluation.

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The Intuitive Data Recorder (IDR) will be used to capture video at 720p and 30fps from one channel of the endoscope on da Vinci Xi or Si system

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The videos will be captured at 720p and 30fps from one channel of the endoscope on da Vinci Xi or Si system

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data will be collected at 2 Intuitive Surgical training labs

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Experience of study participants will mostly be beginners (early in their learning curve) with a few experts (practicing surgeons) if possible.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context

information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case in this challenge will comprise of a video of a surgical training being performed on a porcine model. These videos will be long and variable in length where multiple surgical training steps will be present in each video along with different surgical tools.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

We will have 200+ cases for training and 50+ for testing. We will ensure variability in the dataset through the variety of tasks completed on the porcine model on different anatomy. Each case has an average length of around 4 hrs.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The numbers indicated were kept keeping in mind data collection technicalities and to provide enough data to the participants for developing meaningful models

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

We will try to ensure that the dataset has a balanced range of different tools and surgical steps within the training and testing set. We expect our dataset to have around 10+ unique tool labels with unequal distribution across classes (as some tools occur much more often than other e.g. needle driver) while the surgical step distribution will be much more balanced across training and testing sets.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

N/A

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

We will use a crowd to annotate tool bounding boxes for our testing set. The annotations will not be redundant as bounding box annotations are not that subjective. The surgical step annotations will be done by a team of domain knowledge experts for training and testing sets.

At least 5 annotators for bounding boxes and 2-3 annotators for step annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For test set annotation, the crowd-sourced annotators were already trained and experienced in spatial annotation for surgical tools. Each frame will be annotated then reviewed by the annotation team to ensure quality.

Bounding box labels will be placed around the surgical tools along with an object ID for object tracking. Additional tool classification label, such as left or right side will also be annotated. For surgical steps, the annotators will be

provided by clear step starting and ending times for annotations.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Annotators will have significant experience in labelling bounding boxes for surgical tools and surgical steps.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

n/a

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Raw video frames will not be altered

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Image annotation will only be needed for the test set. Main sources of error would include the bounding box not being "tight" around the tool. It's hard to estimate the error quantitatively but we don't expect it to be more than 5%. For surgical steps, there can be some sources of error as this type of annotation is temporal in nature. However, as the robotic surgical training steps are very well defined (as opposed to steps in clinical procedures), we do not expect there to be any significant error in annotations (<5%)

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

The tool presence labels will be generated using the events stream from the da Vinci system. There is a possibility of a dropped event that can cause error in the training tool presence labels. However, we do not expect this to happen frequently. The step labels would not have any other relevant source of error.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

average f-1 score across all steps will be used to assess performance of surgical step prediction algorithms

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The surgical step category is a standard classification problem where average f1-score can accurately measure the performance of the models

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The performance rank will be based on the rank of the evaluation metric (e.g average f-1 score for surgical step recognition) - the higher the value of this metric, the higher the ranking of that team will be

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results will be penalized and no score will be given for those cases

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Using the standard metrics being used within the activity recognition research seems like the right way to rank teams. For step recognition, we would want to consider precision and recall together for prediction quality, hence mean f1-score will reward and penalize the predictions for correct/incorrect predictions accordingly.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Standard statistical methods to test for significance in results like t-test, ANOVA etc., will be used. Bootstrapping will also be used for uncertainty analysis.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The stated statistical methods are fairly standard and used extensively in literature to test for statistical significance and uncertainty of prediction models.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Additional analysis will be performed on the results to check for ranking variability e.g per class metrics to see if rankings change if any step is ignored in evaluation

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

Please see the cover letter attached (explaining about our change from 3 challenges tasks to 2) as supplemental material, along with annotation protocols and dataset morsel.

Following are arxiv links to the publications from some of our previous challenges within EndoVis:

2020: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2102.13644>

2021: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2212.04448>

2022: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2305.07152>

Please also see the sample data attached as supplemental material which contains 1 case data (video and corresponding task/step labels). The dataset to be used for 2025 lighthouse challenge will be an extension of the dataset used this year at SurgVU 2024. The complete training dataset for SurgVU 2024 can be accessed at <https://storage.googleapis.com/isi-surgvu/surgvu24.zip>.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A